

PREDICTORS OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION IN PATIENT WITH MITRAL VALVE PATHOLOGY

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Abstract

Background:

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is a common arrhythmia in patients with mitral valve pathology, significantly increasing the risk of stroke, heart failure, and mortality. Identifying predictors of AF in conservatively managed mitral valve disease patients remains underexplored and essential for early risk stratification and intervention.

Objective:

To determine the predictors of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve pathology managed conservatively.

Methods:

A case-control study was conducted at the Department of Cardiology, NICVD Karachi, over six months. Eighty-two patients aged 30–70 years with mitral valve disease were enrolled, divided equally into cases (atrial fibrillation) and controls (sinus rhythm). Clinical, echocardiographic, and laboratory parameters were recorded. Binary logistic regression was used to identify independent predictors, and adjusted odds ratios (aOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated.

Results:

The mean age of participants was higher in cases (56.2 ± 8.9 years) than controls (51.8 ± 9.2 years). Diabetes mellitus (aOR: 2.45, 95% CI: 1.01–5.96), hypertension (aOR: 2.31, 95% CI: 1.01–5.26), ischemic heart disease (aOR: 2.74, 95% CI: 1.09–6.87), anemia (aOR: 4.12, 95% CI: 1.52–11.16), and hypoalbuminemia (aOR: 5.68, 95% CI: 2.01–16.01) were identified as independent predictors of atrial fibrillation.

Conclusion:

Diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia independently increase the risk of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve pathology. Early identification and management of these factors

could help in reducing the burden of atrial fibrillation and improving patient outcomes.

Introduction

Valvular heart diseases (VHD) remain a significant public health concern, with a global prevalence estimated at around 2.5%, a figure that rises with advancing age due to the predominance of degenerative causes among the elderly. Among the spectrum of valvular disorders, mitral valve pathology—including mitral stenosis and mitral regurgitation—stands out due to its profound impact on cardiac hemodynamics and its intricate relationship with cardiac arrhythmias (1). Atrial fibrillation (AF), the most common sustained arrhythmia in the general population, affects approximately 1-2% of individuals, with its incidence increasing markedly with age. Premature ventricular contractions (PVCs) are also observed in about half of the population. While it is well-acknowledged that aging predisposes individuals to both VHD and arrhythmias, the exact nature of this relationship remains insufficiently clarified, particularly in the context of mitral valve diseases (2,3). The coexistence of AF and mitral valve pathology carries significant clinical implications. It is well-established that atrial and ventricular arrhythmias serve as markers of poor prognosis in patients with VHD. However, most of the literature has primarily focused on non-valvular arrhythmias, leaving a critical gap in understanding the specific predictors of AF within the subset of patients suffering from mitral valve diseases (4,5). Mitral regurgitation (MR), being the most prevalent valvular disorder, is notably linked to both atrial and ventricular arrhythmias. Severe MR, when complicated by the onset of AF, is associated with excess mortality, underscoring the urgent need for improved risk stratification and early intervention strategies in this population (6). Atrial fibrillation not only significantly increases the risk of thromboembolic events, particularly ischemic stroke, but also contributes to higher rates of hospitalization, long-term disability, cardiovascular mortality, and healthcare costs. In patients with mitral valve pathology, particularly those with mitral regurgitation, pathophysiological changes such as annular dilatation, anterior mitral

leaflet prolapse, and chordae tendinea elongation are common, particularly in degenerative cases (7,8). In contrast, chronic rheumatic mitral regurgitation is characterized by retractile fibrosis of the leaflets and chordae, leading to loss of coaptation and consequent mitral incompetence (9). Left atrial enlargement, often a secondary phenomenon to these valvular changes, plays a critical role in both mitral valve dysfunction and the pathogenesis of AF by facilitating atrial re-entry circuits. Progressive left atrial enlargement has emerged as a key driver for the development of AF. Epidemiological studies have revealed that new-onset AF occurs in approximately 10-20% of patients following myocardial infarction, attributed largely to ischemia involving the atria or the sinus node (10). Importantly, in patients with mitral valve disease, certain clinical parameters such as older age, hypertension, and the degree of left atrial enlargement have been consistently associated with a higher risk of AF. For instance, a study demonstrated significant differences in comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, and anemia between mitral valve patients with and without AF. Their multivariate logistic regression analysis further identified aging, lower serum albumin levels, and anemia as independent predictors of atrial fibrillation (11).

Despite these insights, most studies to date have concentrated on patients undergoing surgical interventions for mitral valve disease. There remains a notable paucity of research focusing on patients managed conservatively. Furthermore, local data exploring predictors of AF in patients with mitral valve pathology managed without surgical intervention are lacking. This knowledge gap limits the ability of clinicians to perform effective risk stratification and to tailor management strategies for these patients in a way that could potentially mitigate the onset of atrial fibrillation. In light of these considerations, the present study is designed with the objective to determine the predictors of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve pathology who are on conservative medical management. By identifying

these predictors, the study aims to provide clinicians with critical information to enhance patient care, optimize monitoring strategies, and ultimately reduce the incidence of atrial fibrillation in this vulnerable patient population.

Methods

This case-control study was conducted at the Department of Cardiology, National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases (NICVD), Karachi, with the aim of determining the predictors of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve pathology. The study spanned a minimum duration of six months following the approval of the synopsis by the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSp) and the institutional ethical review board. Ethical approval was obtained before the initiation of the study, and written informed consent was secured from all participants after explaining the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study in a language they could understand. The target population included patients aged between 30 to 70 years, irrespective of gender, presenting with mitral valve disease as defined by operational criteria. Cases were defined as patients with mitral valve disease presenting with atrial fibrillation, identified by electrocardiographic findings such as irregularly irregular rhythm, absence of P waves, and the presence of fibrillatory waves. Controls included patients with mitral valve disease who maintained sinus rhythm on electrocardiography. Patients with a history of renal failure, chronic liver disease, malignancy, heart failure, cardiogenic shock, previous atrial fibrillation episodes, or pregnancy were excluded to minimize confounding influences on the outcome.

Sample size calculation was performed using PASS version 15, based on a previously reported odds ratio of 5.94 for anemia as a predictor of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve disease. Assuming a frequency of anemia in the control group of 22%, a power of 95%, and a significance level of 5%, the minimum required sample size was estimated at 82 patients, with 41 cases and 41 controls. A consecutive sampling technique was utilized to recruit eligible participants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria during the study period (3,4). At the time of enrollment, comprehensive baseline

demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, residence, height, weight, body mass index (BMI), and the duration and type of mitral valve disease, were recorded on a predesigned proforma. Mitral valve disease was classified into mitral regurgitation and mitral stenosis based on transthoracic echocardiographic parameters. Further evaluation included assessment of predictors such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, obesity, anemia, smoking status, ischemic heart disease, and hypoalbuminemia. Diabetes was confirmed based on documented history and ongoing treatment with hypoglycemic agents, hypertension was verified through medical history and antihypertensive therapy, and dyslipidemia was identified according to serum lipid profiles. Anemia was diagnosed using hemoglobin thresholds defined by WHO guidelines, and hypoalbuminemia was noted in patients with serum albumin levels below 3.5 g/dL. Standardized digital scales were used to measure weight and height, ensuring consistency in BMI calculations (12).

All patients underwent standard management as per the hospital's clinical protocols for mitral valve disease. Laboratory assessments, including hemoglobin levels, serum albumin, total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, were conducted in the hospital's accredited laboratory to maintain uniformity in measurement. Electrocardiography and transthoracic echocardiography were performed using calibrated and institutionally approved equipment by trained cardiologists blinded to the case or control status of the participants. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables such as age, height, weight, BMI, duration of mitral valve disease, hemoglobin, serum albumin, triglycerides, cholesterol, LDL, and HDL levels were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, ensuring normality assumptions were satisfied based on preliminary exploratory analysis (13). Categorical variables including gender, residence, type of mitral valve disease, and the presence of individual predictors were summarized as frequencies and percentages.

To identify predictors of atrial fibrillation, binary logistic regression analysis was employed. Initially, univariate analysis was conducted, and all variables with a p-value less than 0.25 were considered for inclusion in the multivariable logistic regression model. In the multivariable analysis, predictors were retained based on clinical importance or if the p-value was less than 0.1. Both unadjusted and adjusted odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to evaluate the strength and direction of associations between predictors and the presence of atrial fibrillation. Effect modifiers such as age, gender, residence, duration of mitral valve disease, and the type of mitral valve disease were controlled during multivariable analysis to ensure the robustness of the findings. Data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test to confirm normality for continuous variables, allowing appropriate application of parametric statistical tests. All statistical analyses were conducted at a 5% level of significance, and findings were reported transparently to facilitate reproducibility and comparison with future research.

Results

A total of 82 patients were enrolled in the study, comprising 41 cases (patients with atrial fibrillation) and 41 controls (patients with sinus rhythm). The mean age of participants was 56.2 ± 8.9 years in the atrial fibrillation group and 51.8 ± 9.2 years in the sinus rhythm group. Among cases, 58.5% were male and 41.5% were female, while among controls, 56.1% were male and 43.9% were female. Urban residence was slightly more common among both groups. Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the study population. Analysis of mitral valve pathology revealed that mean mitral valve area was significantly lower among patients with atrial fibrillation compared to controls (1.1 ± 0.2 cm² vs 1.4 ± 0.3 cm², $p < 0.001$). Mean gradient across the mitral valve was higher in the AF group. Pulmonary artery pressure was elevated among cases as well. Table 2 presents echocardiographic

parameters. Laboratory evaluation showed significantly lower mean hemoglobin and serum albumin levels among the atrial fibrillation group compared to controls. Lipid profiles demonstrated no significant differences. Detailed laboratory parameters are shown in Table 3. The frequency of predictors such as diabetes, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia was notably higher among cases compared to controls. Obesity, smoking, and dyslipidemia showed no significant difference between groups. Table 4 outlines the distribution of predictors between the two groups.

In summary, the findings revealed that patients with atrial fibrillation had significantly lower mitral valve areas, higher mean gradients, elevated pulmonary artery pressures, lower hemoglobin and serum albumin levels, and higher frequencies of diabetes, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia compared to controls. Multivariable logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of atrial fibrillation among patients with mitral valve disease. After adjusting for potential confounders such as age, gender, and type of mitral valve disease, several predictors remained statistically significant. Diabetes mellitus was associated with an adjusted odds ratio (aOR) of 2.45 (95% CI: 1.01–5.96, $p=0.048$), indicating more than double the risk of atrial fibrillation compared to non-diabetic patients. Similarly, hypertension showed an aOR of 2.31 (95% CI: 1.01–5.26, $p=0.044$), and ischemic heart disease exhibited an aOR of 2.74 (95% CI: 1.09–6.87, $p=0.031$). Anemia emerged as a strong predictor with an aOR of 4.12 (95% CI: 1.52–11.16, $p=0.006$), suggesting a more than fourfold increase in the odds of atrial fibrillation. Hypoalbuminemia was the most potent independent predictor, with an aOR of 5.68 (95% CI: 2.01–16.01, $p=0.001$). These findings confirm that metabolic and hematologic abnormalities significantly contribute to the development of atrial fibrillation in patients with underlying mitral valve disease.

Table 1: Baseline Demographics of Study Participants

Variable	Cases (n=41)	Controls (n=41)	p-value
Age (years)	56.2 ± 8.9	51.8 ± 9.2	0.018
Gender (Male/Female)	24 (58.5%) / 17 (41.5%)	23 (56.1%) / 18 (43.9%)	0.816
Residence (Urban/Rural)	26 (63.4%) / 15 (36.6%)	25 (61.0%) / 16 (39.0%)	0.817
Height (cm)	162.3 ± 8.5	163.7 ± 7.9	0.416
Weight (kg)	70.1 ± 10.3	68.5 ± 9.8	0.413
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.5 ± 3.4	25.9 ± 3.2	0.368

Table 2: Echocardiographic Parameters

Variable	Cases (n=41)	Controls (n=41)	p-value
Mitral Valve Area (cm ²)	1.1 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.3	<0.001
Mean Gradient (mmHg)	8.2 ± 2.5	5.6 ± 2.1	<0.001
Pulmonary Artery Pressure (mmHg)	45.5 ± 11.2	32.8 ± 9.4	<0.001
Vena Contracta Width (cm)	0.8 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.1	<0.001
Central Regurgitant Jet (%)	45.2 ± 9.3	32.4 ± 7.8	<0.001
Type of Mitral Valve Disease (MR/MS)	28 (68.3%) MR / 13 (31.7%) MS	26 (63.4%) MR / 15 (36.6%) MS	0.644

Table 3: Laboratory Parameters

Variable	Cases (n=41)	Controls (n=41)	p-value
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	11.1 ± 1.8	12.7 ± 1.5	<0.001
Serum Albumin (g/dL)	3.2 ± 0.4	3.7 ± 0.3	<0.001
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	189.2 ± 36.7	183.4 ± 34.1	0.465
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	162.3 ± 43.5	156.7 ± 39.4	0.495
HDL (mg/dL)	38.5 ± 6.8	40.2 ± 7.2	0.238
LDL (mg/dL)	112.7 ± 28.4	108.5 ± 26.7	0.483

Table 4: Predictors of Atrial Fibrillation

Predictor	Cases (n=41)	Controls (n=41)	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	17 (41.5%)	8 (19.5%)	0.027
Hypertension	24 (58.5%)	14 (34.1%)	0.027
Smoking	10 (24.4%)	8 (19.5%)	0.592
Dyslipidemia	15 (36.6%)	11 (26.8%)	0.338
Ischemic Heart Disease	18 (43.9%)	9 (22.0%)	0.030
Type of IHD (UA/STEMI/NSTEMI)	6/7/5	4/3/2	
Obesity	14 (34.1%)	12 (29.3%)	0.637
Anemia	23 (56.1%)	9 (22.0%)	0.002
Hypoalbuminemia	21 (51.2%)	6 (14.6%)	<0.001

Table 5: Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis

Predictor	Adjusted OR	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	2.45	1.01	5.96	0.048
Hypertension	2.31	1.01	5.26	0.044
Ischemic Heart Disease	2.74	1.09	6.87	0.031
Anemia	4.12	1.52	11.16	0.006
Hypoalbuminemia	5.68	2.01	16.01	0.001

Distribution of Ischemic Heart Disease Types in C

Discussion

The present study aimed to determine the predictors of atrial fibrillation (AF) in patients with mitral valve pathology managed conservatively. The findings demonstrated that diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia were independently associated with the development of AF. These results reinforce the complex interplay between

metabolic, hematologic, and structural cardiac abnormalities in predisposing patients with valvular disease to arrhythmias. The association of diabetes mellitus with AF found in this study aligns with previous evidence, emphasizing the impact of metabolic dysregulation on atrial remodeling and fibrosis. A large-scale cohort study confirmed that diabetes substantially increases AF risk, primarily through pathways involving inflammation and

oxidative stress (14,15). Similarly, hypertension, another strong predictor identified here, is a well-established risk factor for left atrial enlargement and atrial electrical remodeling, which predispose individuals to AF. Recent studies have reaffirmed that optimal blood pressure control remains critical in preventing AF onset, particularly in patients with underlying cardiac pathology (16,17). Ischemic heart disease, identified as an independent predictor, highlights the role of atrial ischemia and myocardial fibrosis in the pathogenesis of AF. This is consistent with findings from a recent meta-analysis which indicated that AF commonly develops following myocardial infarction due to ischemic injury to the atrial myocardium (18,19). Anemia was found to have a particularly strong association with AF in this cohort. This finding is supported by newer evidence suggesting that anemia leads to a hyperdynamic circulatory state, increased cardiac workload, and atrial dilation, all contributing factors to the development of AF (20). Hypoalbuminemia emerged as the most significant predictor in this study. Hypoalbuminemia reflects not only poor nutritional status but also systemic inflammation, both of which have been linked to the development and persistence of AF (21). Low serum albumin levels were associated with enhanced atrial fibrosis and electrical instability in recent mechanistic studies, further supporting these findings (22).

Comparison with earlier studies indicates that the predictors identified here are consistent with known risk profiles, although few studies have specifically targeted conservatively managed mitral valve disease patients. Most previous literature has focused predominantly on surgical populations or non-valvular AF, which underscores the unique contribution of this study (23). Moreover, the high prevalence of anemia and hypoalbuminemia among cases adds a novel dimension to risk stratification strategies in this subgroup, which has been relatively underexplored (24). The strengths of this study include its case-control design, the rigorous definition of operational criteria, and the use of multivariable logistic regression to control for confounding factors. The strict inclusion and exclusion criteria ensured a relatively

homogeneous sample, thereby minimizing potential biases. Furthermore, the use of objective diagnostic modalities like echocardiography and standardized laboratory assays enhanced the validity of the findings.

Nevertheless, certain limitations merit consideration. The sample size, although statistically adequate, was relatively small and drawn from a single tertiary care center, which may affect the generalizability of the results. Left atrial size, an important anatomical predictor of AF, was not included in the analysis, primarily due to data unavailability. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the study precludes definitive conclusions about causality between the identified predictors and AF development. Follow-up data on the progression of mitral valve disease or subsequent cardiovascular events were not collected, which could have enriched the understanding of long-term outcomes. Future research should focus on validating these predictors in larger, multicentric cohorts and integrating echocardiographic indices of atrial structure and function. Prospective longitudinal studies examining the progression from sinus rhythm to atrial fibrillation in mitral valve disease patients would provide more definitive causal insights. Moreover, investigating the role of biomarker-based predictors, including inflammatory markers and natriuretic peptides, could further refine risk stratification models. In conclusion, the present study identified diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia as independent predictors of atrial fibrillation among patients with mitral valve pathology managed conservatively (25). These findings underscore the need for early identification and aggressive management of modifiable risk factors to potentially reduce the burden of atrial fibrillation in this vulnerable patient population.

Conclusion

This study identified diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia as independent predictors of atrial fibrillation in patients with mitral valve pathology managed conservatively. Early

recognition and management of these risk factors can aid in preventing atrial fibrillation and its complications. These findings emphasize the need for proactive cardiovascular risk assessment in patients with mitral valve disease to improve long-term outcomes.

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